

Growth and performance of small-scale industries in Karnataka region: An overview

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Abstract

Small-scale industries (SSIs) are a significant sector of the Indian economy. The study was to examine the growth and performance of small-scale industries. The study was carried out using secondary data and a descriptive research proposal to identify the problems and remedial measures for small-scale industries in India, the data was collected from 2010–11 to 2021–22. The study reveals a disparity in industry growth and financial support in Karnataka, despite the government's liberalization of investment and industry establishment. The lack of financial support, lack of raw materials, lack of organized marketing, and additional issues in small-scale industries led to a significant variation in the number of industries, investments, and employment in these enterprises during the selected period. The results are finally there. The study reveals a positive correlation between various industries, investment, and employment in the economy, with a minimum correlation of zero and a high degree of positive correlation between employment and investment. The government should support small-scale industries (SSIs) by identifying weaker ones, providing financial assistance, and promoting their effectiveness and competitiveness in a market-based economy.

Keywords: Units, growth, employment, investment, policies

1. Introduction

Approximately 8.5 lakh people work in Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) in Karnataka, while the number of employees is above 55 lakh and rising annually. Additionally, Karnataka has received investments of around Rs. 4 lakh crores over the previous five years, placing it sixth in the nation for industrial growth. MSMEs foster entrepreneurship and provide a sizable number of job opportunities, both of which have a major positive impact on the expansion of the economy. MSMEs support the expansion of the industrial sector by providing input goods and services to larger businesses. Numerous laws, plans, incentives, and concessions have been put into place thanks to the assistance of MSMEs.

The industries of the state are now experiencing losses as a result of the lockdown that followed the COVID-19 virus pandemic two years ago and the halted exports that followed. Certain industries have ceased to exist. In the

meanwhile, the federal and state governments have provided some assistance. But it will take some time for these industries to return to their previous standing. MSMEs have a range of challenges that may be resolved by implementing the following strategies: Enhancing funding, increasing equity capital, enhancing efficiency through management strategies, and simplifying corporate operations are a few of the objectives.

2. Review of Literature

1. Nalla Bala Kalyan Kumar and Dr. Sardar Gugloth. (2012) ^[1]. the study of their advice for MSMEs, with a focus on the ongoing changes in the business environment. The impact of local and international liberalization on SMEs is also highlighted and evaluated. MSMEs have emerged as the most dynamic sector of the Indian manufacturing economy.
2. Ram Singh, Dr. O P Verma and Dr Bimal Anjum. (*et*

- al.* 2012) ^[2]. This industry now offers more opportunities thanks to the growth of small firms in India and the focus on enacting legislative improvements. Technology development and financial infrastructure construction are required to meet growth objectives and boost SSI.
3. Hitendra Bargal, *et al.* (2009) ^[3]. In terms of quantity, output, employment, and exports, the expansion of the small-scale sector directly affects the growth of the total economy. Gaining insight into its significance for the development of the nation's economy might be helpful.
 4. S. Pratibha. (2018) ^[4]. expansion and performance of the small-scale sector as indicated by the most recent gains in employment, working units, and investment levels. This article also aims to identify the current issues these units are facing as well as the government's policy objectives.
 5. M.H. Bala Subrahmanya. (2005) ^[5]. Argues that raising labour productivity might be a different approach to boosting energy efficiency in small, energy-intensive enterprises in developing nations like India, which struggle with the cost of upgrading equipment to increase energy efficiency.
 6. Dr Seethamma K and Sarvesha HK (2020) ^[6]. The advent of new industries should not halt the expansion and development of SSI units. Resources should be allocated to the creation of SSIs by the government and other entities participating in the process.
 7. Dr P Hari kumar and Dr M. Chandraiah. (2015) ^[7]. The analysis concluded that the period's low return on capital was caused by high manufacturing costs. The SSI industry must cope with an increasing number of obstacles and credit-related problems as it gets ready for new participants.
 8. Dr. Prakasha. (2019) ^[8]. Usually, smaller units visit a more advanced unit or hear about technological possibilities through word-of-mouth. Purchasing commodities of a long-term nature, such as land and buildings, machinery, cookware, furniture, and other items, also need long- and medium-term financing. The prompt and appropriate acquisition of finance is a critical factor in the success of small-scale enterprises.
 9. Subhamoy Banik. (2018) ^[9]. This article's study fortifies the SSI sector, enabling it to occupy its proper position within the Indian economy's growth mechanism. To make the most of their innate potential and thrive in human and economic activities, MSMEs require assistance and training. In conclusion, the research attempts to explore the role that small-scale enterprises have played in economic development as well as the challenges that these sectors have encountered.

3. Research gap

Reading the information above reveals how previous research was organized. Research on the next stage of small-scale enterprises and issues has received increased attention from 1992–1993 to 2009–2010; state, district, and Taluk-level studies have previously been conducted in this regard. However, this study examines ongoing data collected between 2010–11 and 2021–22. In conclusion, this study offers some suggestions.

4. Need for the study

The primary goals of the study are to decrease small-scale businesses' challenges and to assist them. A crisis on the manufacturing and marketing fronts is among the many problems that small businesses have faced recently. Historically, small businesses have faced challenges related to technology, energy and raw material shortages, competitive marketing against larger industries, funding and credit limitations, and other issues. The researcher believed that a thorough analysis of the many problems and opportunities that existed was essential to strengthening and addressing the intrinsic limitations of small-scale businesses. The researcher decided to investigate this topic as a result.

5. Scope of the study

To study the performance of small-scale industry in Karnataka, data covered from 2011-12 to 202-22.

6. Objectives of the study

This study's specific objectives are to analyses:

1. To examine the growth and performance of small-scale industries Kalyana Karnataka Region.
2. To determine the issues facing Karnataka's small-scale industries Kalyana Karnataka Region.

7. Hypotheses of study

H₀: There is no significant difference between the number of Units/industries, investment, and employment during the selected period.

H₁: There is a significant difference between the number of Units/industries, investment, and employment during a selected period.

8. Collection of data

The research approach used in the study was descriptive, and secondary data collected between 2010–2011 and 2021–2022 were used. Information was gathered from a variety of sources, including publications, articles, yearly reports published by the government, the Karnataka Economic Survey, MSME, and GOI websites, among others.

9. Tools of Exploration

Instruments for doing small-scale industrial analysis the terms ANOVA, Minimum and Maximum, Percentages Sample Variance, Standard Deviation, Correlation, Descriptive Statistics, and Ranking.

10. Small-scale industry in Karnataka scenario 2021-22

Karnataka is regarded for being a top commercial location. Over 8.5 lakh Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises (MSMEs) can be found in Karnataka today, and they employ over 55 lakh people. The main industries are those that produce ready-to-wear, process food, engineer, operate foundries, make cars, operate chemical plants, make handicrafts, etc. Karnataka has also historically been home to small-scale, rural, and handicraft-related industries. One of them is Khadi. One of Asia's largest industrial zones, Bengaluru's Peenya Industrial Area is home to numerous MSMEs. The goods made here are well-known around the world.

The growth of small-scale companies is one of the most important components of our nation's planned economic growth after independence. We are aware that the notion of small-scale industries merely wasn't popular when the country was on the edge of becoming independent. All over our country, there were rural and cottage businesses that constituted the "indigenous sector" of our industry. Several initiatives to maintain, modernize, and advance this set of industries were begun soon after independence, and these initiatives eventually evolved into the current small-scale industrial program. Small businesses have played a significant role in the rise of industrial entrepreneurship in the middle class by providing competent technicians and young educated men from that stratum of society with the opportunity to go into business for themselves. Tiny-scale industries (SSI) are denoted as micro-scale companies that produce goods or provide services with the aid of relatively small machines and a sparse workforce. The MSMEs of service and manufacturing organizations have been split into three categories: micro, small, and medium firms, depending on the amount of investment made in structures and equipment.

11. To examine the growth and performance of small-scale industries

Table 1: Classification of MSME is based on Turnover and Investments as below

Updated MSME Definition and Criteria in 2024		
Type of enterprise	Investment	Turnover
Micro	Rs 1 crore	Rs 5 crore
Small	Rs 10 crore	Rs 50 crore
Medium	Rs 50 crore	Rs 250 crore

Sources: <https://razorpay.com/learn/new-msme-definition-turnover-2020/>

Table 2: Karnataka all Districts Registered (MSME) Small Units, Invest and Employment for The Year 2020-21 Up to 30 November 2021

Summary	Small (up to Rs. 10.00 crore investment or 50 crore turnover)		
	Industries	Invest (Rs. Crs.)	Employment (thousand)
Total	580	889.1	9930
Mean	19.33333	29.63667	331
Median	12	18.595	208
Standard Deviation	29.70003	43.64684	525.9155
Sample Variance	882.092	1905.046	276587.1
Range	168	240.74	2884
Minimum	2	2.1	31
Maximum	170	242.84	2915

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-2022

The above table displays that the number of registered small units, investment, and employment in the year 2020–21 is 580, total investment is 889.1 crore, and total employment is 9930. The mean value of the above units is 19.33, the mean value of investment (Rs. Crs.) is 29.63667, and the mean value of employment is 331. a minimum of 2 units in the Kodagu district. The maximum number of units is 170 in Bengaluru (urban). The minimum investment is Rs. 2.1 crores in Kodagu, with a maximum investment of Rs. 242.84 crores in Bengaluru (Urban). Ballari has the most

employment opportunities (611 in total). And lastly, the number of registered small units, investment, and employment in conflict value.

Table 3: The number of micro-units, investments, and employment for the Kalyana Karnataka region in 2020-21. November 30, 2021

Sl. No.	Districts	Small (investment of up to Rs. 10.00 crore, or 50 crores)		
		Units	Invest (Rs. Crs)	Employment 0000 (thousand)
1	Ballari	22	21.44	611
2	Bidar	15	31.89	235
3	Kalaburagi	23	37.84	285
4	Koppal	18	23.7	198
5	Raichur	27	3.05	390
6	Yadgir	5	13.11	78
7	Vijayanagara	-	-	-
Total		110	131.03	1797
Mean		18.33333	21.83833	299.5
Median		20	22.57	260
Standard Deviation		7.737355	12.569	183.8246
Sample Variance		59.86667	157.9798	33791.5
Minimum		5	3.05	78
Maximum		27	37.84	611

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-2022

The above table displays the number of Micro units registered, investments made, and employment for 2020–2021. Kalyana Karnataka region the total number of industries is 110, total investment is 131.03 crore, and total employment is 1797. The mean value of the above units is 18.33, the mean value of an investment is Rs. Crs Rs. 21.83, and the mean value of employment is 299.5. minimum of 5 units in Yadgir district. The maximum units are 27 Raichur. The minimum investment is Rs. 3.05 crores in Raichur district, with a maximum investment of Rs. Crs 37.84, Kalaburagi district. Ballari has the most employment opportunities (611 in total).

Table 4: Growth of SSI units in Karnataka (2010-11) to (2020-21)

Sl. No.	Year	No of SSI Industries	Increase or decrease	% of Increase or Decrease	Ranking
1	2010-11	413284	0	0	10
2	2011-12	434305	21021	5.09	9
3	2012-13	458511	24206	5.57	8
4	2013-14	484549	26038	5.68	7
5	2014-15	513291	28742	5.93	6
6	2015-16	538947	25656	5	5
7	2016-17	578117	39170	7.27	4
8	2017-18	626599	48482	8.39	3
9	2018-19	695877	69278	11.06	2
10	2019-20	793109	97232	13.97	1
11	2020-21*	332233	-460876	-58.11	2

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-2022

The figure directly above shows the growth of SSI units, the number of units, and the change in ranking units in Karnataka's small-scale industries from 2010–2011 to 2020–21. From the table, it is clear the number of small-scale industry units increased from 413284 in 2010–11 to 332233 in 2020–21. In 2019–20, when there was a growth of 97232 units, the percentage of growth was at its highest. The

increase of SSI units in Karnataka went from 5.09% in 2010–11 to 13.97% in 2019–20 during the study period, and

the state also ranks first. As in the period 2010–2011, its rate of increase reached its lowest, 5.09%.

Table 5: Increase in SSI investment units in Karnataka (2010-11) to (2020-21)

Sl. No.	Year	Invest (Rs. in Lakh)	Increase or decrease	Percentage of Increase or Decrease	Ranking
1	2010-11	1239873	0	0	11
2	2011-12	1399514	159641	12.88	10
3	2012-13	1616365	216851	15.49	9
4	2013-14	1901082	284717	17.61	8
5	2014-15	2180373	279291	14.69	7
6	2015-16	2674965	494592	22.68	6
7	2016-17	3941379	1266414	47.34	5
8	2017-18	5099954	1158575	29.4	4
9	2018-19	6587652	1487698	29.17	2
10	2019-20	8447379	1859727	28.23	1
11	2020-21*	6000678	-2446701	-28.96	1

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-2022

The table above illustrates the investments in small-scale industrial units in Karnataka from 2010-2011 to 2020-2021. According to the data, the investment value of the small-scale industries sector in Karnataka increased from Rs. 1239873 lakhs in 2010–11 to Rs. 6000678 lakhs in 2020–

21. With growth of Rs. 1859727 lakhs from the previous year, the 2019–20 period has experienced the highest percentage increase. Additionally, the biggest expenditure for 2019–20. This grade is 1, and the anticipated investment for the following year is 244670.

Table 6: Employment growth in the SSI sector in Karnataka (2010-11) to (2020-21)

Sl. No.	Year	Employment in 000s (in thousand)	Increase or decrease	% of Increase or Decrease	Ranking
1	2010-11	2396	0	0	11
2	2011-12	2524	128	5.34	10
3	2012-13	2680	156	6.18	9
4	2013-14	2846	166	6.19	8
5	2014-15	3022	176	6.18	7
6	2015-16	3243	221	7.31	6
7	2016-17	3752	509	15.7	4
8	2017-18	4193	441	11.75	3
9	2018-19	4776	583	13.9	2
10	2019-20	5478	702	14.7	1
11	2020-21*	3631	-1847	-33.72	1

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-2022

Table 7: Small-scale industrial unit registration in Karnataka (2010-11) to (2020-21)

Sl. No.	Year	Number of SSI industries	Invest (Rs. in Lakh)	Employment in 000s (thousand)
1	2010-11	413284	1239873	2396
2	2011-12	434305	1399514	2524
3	2012-13	458511	1616365	2680
4	2013-14	484549	1901082	2846
5	2014-15	513291	2180373	3022
6	2015-16	538947	2674965	3243
7	2016-17	578117	3941379	3752
8	2017-18	626599	5099954	4193
9	2018-19	695877	6587652	4776
10	2019-20	793109	8447379	5478
11	2020-21*	332233	6000678	3631
Total		5868822	41089214	38541
Mean		533529.2727	3735383.091	3503.727273
Standard Error		40190.31747	741348.2103	296.4557637
Median		513291	2674965	3243
Standard Deviation		133296.2033	2458773.853	983.2325352
Sample Variance		17767877806	6.05E+12	966746.2182
Minimum		332233	1239873	2396
Maximum		793109	8447379	5478

Sources: Karnataka Economic Survey 2021-2022

The employment near in Karnataka's small-scale industrial parts during the observation period is displayed in the table

just above it, together with year-over-year growth rates and percentage increases over the relevant prior year. One could

see that for 2396 people in 2010–11 until 3631 people in 2020–21, the amount of employment climbed by a %. With a rise in the number of 5478 over the prior years, the percentage growth was largest in the academic year 2019–20, which also had the top ranking. And 3631 people are expected to be employed in the following year, 2020–2021.

The finding: The level of industries, investments, and employment in the economy are all positively and directly correlated.

The analysis of the number of SSI units, investment (Rs. in

Lack), and employment in thousands is shown in the table directly above. The total value of SSI Units is 5868822, the mean value is 533529.3, and the next total value investment is 41089214. The mean value is 3735383.091. In 2019–20, the maximum investment value is Rs. 844739 crores. The minimum investment in the year 2010-11 total investment is 1239873. The mean value of employment is 3503.727. The employment of thousands of total employees increased year by year in 2019-20, the maximum number of employees is 5478; in 2010-11, the minimum number of employees is 2396.

Table 8: Results of the registration of small industrial enterprises in Karnataka in correlation.

	Number of SSI Industries	Invest (Rs. in Lakh)	Employment in 000s (thousand)
Number of SSI Industries	1		
Investment (Rs. in Lakh)	0.6629452	1	
Employment in 000s (thousand)	0.84036436	0.961389457	1

The directly above table below displays the results of the correlation analysis. The results show that the investment and number of SSI units' relation is low at 0.66, the

investment with employment correlation is minimum at 0.84, and employment with investment is a direct relation with a high degree of positive correlation at 0.96.

Table 9: Results of ANOVA used to register small industrial entities in Karnataka.

ANOVA						
Source of Difference	SS	DF	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	8.97E+13	2	4.48E+13	22.18719434	0	3.3158295
Within Groups	6.06E+13	30	2.02E+12			
Total	1.50E+14	32				

It shows the results of a one-way ANOVA just above the table. Because the p-value was less than 0.05 at a significant threshold of 5%, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, "there is a significant deviation in the number of industries, investment, and employment in small-scale industries in the selected period" is the alternate hypothesis. Ultimately, the rejection of the null hypothesis (H₀) and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis (H₁) represents the important value.

12. To determine the issues facing Karnataka's small-scale industries

- 1. Inadequate credit support:** The lack of timely and enough financial support is one of the major issues SSIs in India face. The biggest obstacles to the development of SSIs in India are a lack of funding and poor creditworthiness. These tiny borrowers often have poor credit, so they must deal with uncooperative lenders who might only agree to lend at a high interest rate. This is the real and present situation of SSI.
- 2. Inequity and low-quality raw materials:** In order to obtain raw materials, whether from the domestic or international market, an SSI unit must overcome enormous challenges. The issues are brought on by a lack of enough raw materials and the prohibitively expensive, subpar raw resources. The owner of the SSI unit is unaccustomed to buying goods on international markets. Because of economies of scale, large-scale enterprises can get top-notch raw materials for less money, which enables them to charge less for their goods than SSIs.
- 3. The absence of a well-organized marketing process:** An SSI unit does not have a formalized marketing

procedure and even does not designate a marketing entity to handle the marketing of goods or services. As a result, their products' quality is inferior to that of those produced by large-scale industries. When compared to large-scale industries that make significant investments in branding and advertising efforts, they are at a competitive disadvantage.

- 4. Inadequate infrastructure:** The SSI units' potential to develop and thrive is severely hampered by inadequate infrastructure. The bulk of SSI units are found in semi-urban, urban, and rural settings with inadequate electricity to operate heavy equipment, frequent power outages, and limited access to roadways. Due to underutilization of capacity and poor infrastructure, the enterprise's productivity schedule suffers. Additionally, SSIs use outdated machinery, technology, and tools, whereas large-scale businesses benefit from competitive advantages.

13. Additional problems of small-scale industries

1. They cannot make use of industrial economies of scale, for one.
2. Small business entrepreneurs lack enough long- or short-term financing. They consequently lack both fixed assets and working resources.
3. Companies lack the will to develop because those who can't benefit from government incentives and initiatives.
4. The most recent technology isn't used since it is so expensive. Simply said, outmoded methods and techniques are in use.
5. A lack of working capital results in a shortage of raw materials.

6. Because of a lack of power, small firms cannot make use of the entire plant's capabilities.

14. Conclusion and suggestions

This study aims to analyse the SSI growth problems and remedial measures for small-scale industries in Karnataka in this study, the researcher takes small-scale industries' problems such as suggestion and establishment industries, employment and financial assistance. Because the sustainability of SSIs' activities can be provided by fewer products and production than large-scale enterprises, small business owners are unable to compete with large-scale industries, they are less affected by negative circumstances even if they lose markets and the high costs with storing and production problems.

The National Manufacturing Competitiveness Program's eight components-incubator, intellectual property awareness, quality management, technology improvement marketing support, design expertise, and ICT promotion-are intended to increase long-term capacity, ward off foreign competition, and foster robust growth. Government policy should also assist SSIs in increasing their effectiveness and competitiveness in a market-oriented economy.

- Given the greater quality, SSI Industries must increase production, maintain or even increase quality, and innovate.
- This demonstrates that when a small business's technology is similar, boosting labour productivity and efficiency can be an effective tactic for enhancing energy efficiency, generating higher profits, and fortifying competitiveness.

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